

Meghnad Saha: A visionary

Mahesh Chandra Chattopadhyaya[†]

Early Life

Meghnad Saha was born on 6th October 1893 in a poor family in village Seoratali, near Dhaka. He was a brilliant student. Though his parents could not afford to bear the expenses towards Meghnad Saha's education due to poverty, he nevertheless carried on school education by earning merit scholarships. However, he could feel the pain and suffering of poverty of poor people, which created a deep impression in his mind and later on, shaped him to find out solutions of social and economical problems.

At Presidency College in Calcutta (now Kolkata), he came in contact with the visionary Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, who taught him chemistry in B.Sc. Following the footsteps of Acharya Ray, he not only took keen interest in science but also gave enough thought towards balanced development of industries and agriculture in India. He passed his B.Sc. examination in 1913, M.Sc. (Mixed Mathematics) examination in 1915 from Calcutta University. He joined the Department of Mathematics in newly established University College of Science, Calcutta University in 1916 as lecturer. Later on, he was shifted to the Department of Physics in 1917. On the basis of his original research papers, published in *Philosophical Magazine* and *Physics Review*, he was awarded the D.Sc. degree of the Calcutta University in 1918. He went to Europe on a study tour in 1919 and returned to India in 1921 to join Calcutta University as Khaira Professor of Physics. In 1922, his guru Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray summed up the bearing of Dr. Saha's researches on the problem of cosmic radiation in an article published in *Modern Review*¹.

Saha at Allahabad

The University of Allahabad became a residential teaching university by AU Act of 1921. Various teaching departments came into existence as scholars from different parts of India joined these departments as faculties. Meghnad Saha was appointed as Professor and founder Head of the Phys-

ics Department in 1923. Besides teaching B.Sc. and M.Sc. students, Professor Saha, initiated research activities. He verified experimentally his famous 'Theory of Thermal Ionization' using high temperature furnace designed by him. With this furnace he thoroughly analyzed stellar spectra to get complete information about the state of stellar atmosphere. The impetus given to Astrophysics by Saha's work can scarcely be over estimated. The theory of Ionization is one of the few scientific works ever done that have laid the broad foundation for new discipline of science. It established Astrophysics on a firm scientific base in the modern age. He was elected Fellow of the Royal Society of London in 1927.

Saha's Interest in History and Indology

In the Department of Sanskrit and Oriental Languages, University of Allahabad, Pt. Kshetresachandra Chattopadhyaya joined as Lecturer in 1924. Professor Saha and Pt. Chattopadhyaya, besides being the alumni of Presidency College, Calcutta, shared common interest in Ancient History and used to discuss the problems related to ancient Indian history and archaeology. Professor Saha took him and Dr. Dharmananda Koshambi of Aligarh Muslim University to the city Kaushambi on his car. This led to the foundation of their desire to start archeological excavations at Kaushambi and subsequently, they approached the Archeological Survey of India (ASI) to undertake the excavation work. ASI deputed N. G. Majumdar for this work.

Professor Saha's love for Indian history and culture inspired him, not only to study the different aspects of Indology but to go beyond and to discover facts which were not known at that time. He was interested in the decipherment of Harappan script and read a lot in this connection. Professor Saha's interest in history included religions of the world. He had studied the subject very well.

Knowing Professor Saha's interest in Indology, Max

[†]Former President, Indian Chemical Society, Kolkata, India.
E-mail: mcc46@rediffmail.com, mcchattopadhyaya@gmail.com

Planck expressed his desire to study Indian philosophy. Professor Saha made available a book on Indian Philosophy authored by Professor A. C. Mukherjee of Allahabad University.

Saha's Vision for Creation of Organizations

In 1924, Professor Saha wrote an article titled "Plea for a Museum at Allahabad" in Allahabad University magazine, which reflects his vision as well as his vast knowledge of surroundings of Allahabad². He wrote "The ideal museum is not a mere collection of 'curios' or 'specimens'. It should cover the whole range of human activity, in the past or at the present time and should teach the truths of all the sciences. The 'collections' must be arranged in such a manner that it should provide amusement and instructions to all sorts of people. Of course, such a program cannot be fulfilled by a single institution. We have, therefore, new sub-divisions such as Art Museum, Science Museum, Industrial Museum, Anthropological Museum and so forth".

Later on in the same article, Professor Saha describes how the museum could be built. He wrote and I paraphrase – The first duty of science section will be to organize a 'Geological Museum' where specimens of rocks and minerals will be collected and classified from all parts of India, specially places near at home, namely Bundelkhand, The Central Provinces, The Central Indian States and Shivalik Hills". He further adds "The Art section of the museum may specialize in Archeology works of art and sculptures for which many cities in the United Provinces are still famous. It may attach, to itself a section where Hindi and Urdu manuscripts may be collected and preserved". He goes on – "Regarding the archeological section, it is superfluous to add that, Allahabad has great possibilities". The country, round about Allahabad is full of relics of the old days, Hindu and Muhammeden. The Archeological finds at Jhusi (old Pratisthanpur), Kosam (old Kausambi) – capital of King Udayan (celebrated in Buddhist lore), Singraun (old Singverpur – capital of Guhak Chandel, friend of Ramchandra and an old centre of sun worship), Karamanikpur (seats of early Muhammeden rulers), Deora (old Vitabhayapattan) which are all within the Allahabad district and within 30 miles from the city of Allahabad, can find no better name than The Museum at Allahabad. Not merely this, the establishment of a museum at Allahabad, will act as powerful incentive to the public, particularly to the students, hailing from the interior of the province, who collect these

finds and deposit them in the central home at Allahabad.

The glimpse of vision of Professor Saha is further exemplified in his article titled "A Plea for an Academy of Sciences", published in the December 1929 issue of Allahabad University magazine³. He felt the need for scientists to seek a common meeting ground for exchange of ideas. With this in view, the U.P. Academy of Science was formed in 1930 at Allahabad. Thus, Professor Saha's plea became a reality. He was a natural choice for the post of President of the academy, which started with 19 Founder Fellows.

The objective of the academy was not just a scholarly exchange of ideas but an effort to apply science and technology for solving various economic ills affecting the country. Shantimay Chatterjee mentioned in his Saha centenary article⁴ that "It was for the first time that the Indian scientists became aware of his role in finding solutions to natural problems". In 1934, U.P. Academy of Science was renamed as The National Academy of Sciences.

As the President of the Indian Science Congress Association in 1934, Professor Saha made serious efforts for starting an All India Academy of Sciences, which resulted in the formation of National Institute of Sciences; now known as Indian National Science Academy. His vision to develop a strong base of research and scientific man power in India can be understood when he conceived the idea of an institute of nuclear physics as early as 1936 while he was in Allahabad. I would like to mention about Professor Saha's effort in establishment of some more scientific bodies. Professor Nil Ratan Dhar, the Founder Head of Chemistry Department of University of Allahabad, was elected as President of Chemistry Section of Indian Science Congress Association in 1923. Professor Saha and several eminent chemists in the country requested Professor Dhar to initiate steps for the formation of Indian Chemical Society⁵. In May 1924, the Society came into existence with Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray as the Founder President of the Society. Professor Saha contributed his paper titled *On An Experimental test of thermal ionization of Elements* co-authored with Nalinikanta Sur in the very first issue of the Journal of Indian Chemical Society⁶. He also published another paper titled *The Phase Rule and its Application to Problems of Luminescence and Ionization of Gases* in 1925⁷.

In 1935, Professor Saha established another scientific body, Indian Science News Association (ISNA) with his

teacher Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray as President. The nature of the Association was such that it incorporated the cultural activities along with scientific activities which reflected in the journal *Science and Culture* published by the Association. Professor Saha was the Editor of the journal and appointed his best student Gyan Chandra Mukherji as Assistant Editor. The Indian Press, Allahabad used to print the Journal till Professor Saha was in University of Allahabad.

On the occasion of Golden Jubilee Celebrations of University of Allahabad in December, 1937; some interesting and instructive experiments were arranged by Professor Saha for the public. He even went out of his way to help the Municipal Board of Allahabad in solving such issues related to electrical work.

During Professor Saha's tenure at University of Allahabad, eminent scientists used to visit the Physics Department, including Nobel Laureates like Arthur H. Compton, Arnold Sommerfeld, Sir A. Eddington. During Eddington's visit he was accorded a civic reception by the Municipal Board of Allahabad. Compton during his visit to the Department of Physics in February 1927 delivered the following lectures:

- (1) Light Waves and Light Projectiles
- (2) The Architecture of Atoms
- (3) X-rays

Recollecting life and works of Professor Saha, Shantimay Chatterjee wrote⁴ "It was at Allahabad that Saha became FRS, President and General President of Indian Science Congress Association, President of The National Institute of Science. From here he became a Carnegie Fellow. It was in Allahabad; he mastered his knowledge of ancient Indian history, archaeology, ancient astronomy, pleaded for hydraulic research laboratory and predicted the mass of magnetic monopole – which is the only prediction that has yet to be confirmed. It was from Allahabad that Meghnad Saha, emerged as a strong force in the national arena".

Return to Calcutta

C. V. Raman was Palit Professor of Physics during the period 1917-1934. After he left, the Professorship was offered to D. N. Bose, who later became the Director of Bose Institute after the death of Jagdish Chandra Bose in 1937. Saha returned to Calcutta as Palit Professor of Physics in 1938. Considering the importance of nuclear physics, Saha revised the curriculum to provide an opportunity to the stu-

dents to study this new and exciting subject. Thus he became the first person to introduce nuclear physics in the country. With the monetary help from the Tatas, Saha was able to set up cyclotron. He built the Institute of Nuclear Physics, the building of which was declared open in 1951 by Nobel Laureate Irene Joliot Curie.

Science and Culture

In Calcutta, Professor Saha continued his keen interest in the publication of *Science and Culture*. Besides writing editorial notes, he used to contribute his own articles in the same. Through these articles, he conveyed his ideas on various subjects, ranging from constituents of matter, spectra of comets, solar control of the atmosphere, physics in the aid of medicine to planning for the Damodar Valley. He also made editorial notes on "National Scheme of Education" and on "Archeological Excavations in India". He even persuaded scholars of other disciplines, including Pt. Chattopadhyaya to contribute articles in *Science and Culture*. In the first volume, Pt. Chattopadhyaya contributed the article, titled "A French Account of Ancient India". During Professor Saha's time, the journal *Science and Culture* devoted to its true fundamental objectives – the interpretation of science and its popularization and advocacy of application of science to bring about a technological revolution.

Towards Social Goals

Professor Saha was ahead of his time, particularly when it came to correlating social needs with the growth of science. When Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, the then President of The Indian National Congress addressed the Indian Science News Association in 1938. Professor Saha taking this opportunity was able to convince him to setup the National Planning Committee (NPC). The proceedings of NPC bear deep imprint of Professor Saha's concern towards a full fledged technological revolution in India.

The Presidential address delivered by Professor Saha at the 3rd Annual General meeting of the Indian Physical Society in January, 1937; reflects his concern for problems of India's economic and social development and with the role of scientists in discovery, planning and reform.

One also saw Saha in a new role, that of a people's representative in the Lok Sabha of 1952 parliamentary election. Saha actively participated in the parliament in the area of education, refugee and rehabilitation, atomic energy, multi-

purpose river projects, flood control and long time planning. He was the chief architect of river planning in India and prepared the original plan for the Damodar Valley Project. His speeches in the parliament reveal his deep commitment towards uplifting the masses.

Professor Saha played an important role in fostering the scientific temper and culture in the society. Professor Saha strongly advocated the social and economical planning in India, particularly in Science, Industry and Technology. He was a member of the Planning Commission, Chairman of Power and Fuel Committee and member of sub-committee on River Taming and Irrigation. He was also Chairman of Calendar Reform Committee. To achieve his mission he even

entered in politics. Like his teacher Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, Professor Saha was a visionary in true sense.

References

1. P. C. Ray, *Modern Review*, 1922, **32**, 718.
2. Meghnad Saha, *The Allahabad University Magazine*, 1924, **2**, 13.
3. Meghnad Saha, *The Allahabad University Magazine*, 1929, **7**.
4. Shantimoy Chatterjee, *Saha Centenary Souvenir, Allahabad University*, 1993, 34.
5. N. R. Dhar, *Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray – Life and Achievement, Indian Chemical Society*, 1972, 47.
6. Meghnad Saha and Nalinikanta Sur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **1**, 9.
7. Meghnad Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 49.